

Welcome!

Phase 1: Welcome! This slide introduces the project and lists the team members. It includes a 'Welcome to the team' section with names and roles, and a 'Project overview' section with a brief description of the project's goals and objectives.

Before we start...

Phase 2: Before we start... This slide outlines the initial steps and goals for the project. It includes a 'Project goals' section with a list of objectives and a 'Next steps' section with a timeline of tasks to be completed.

Start here

Phase 3: Start here This slide provides a detailed overview of the project's progress and current status. It includes a 'Project overview' section with a summary of the project's goals and objectives, and a 'Current status' section with a list of tasks and their progress.

Phase one completed!
Well done, solvers! 🎉

Keep working

Phase 4: Keep working This slide focuses on the ongoing work and progress of the project. It includes a 'Project overview' section with a summary of the project's goals and objectives, and a 'Current status' section with a list of tasks and their progress.

Phase two completed!
You're on the right track! 🚀

Keep working

Phase 5: Keep working This slide continues the focus on the ongoing work and progress of the project. It includes a 'Project overview' section with a summary of the project's goals and objectives, and a 'Current status' section with a list of tasks and their progress.

Phase three completed!
You're on your path to success! 🏆

You almost did it!

Phase 6: You almost did it! This slide highlights the final stages of the project and the progress made. It includes a 'Project overview' section with a summary of the project's goals and objectives, and a 'Current status' section with a list of tasks and their progress.

Phase four completed!
You're almost there! 🏁

We're almost done

Phase 7: We're almost done This slide shows the final progress and the completion of most tasks. It includes a 'Project overview' section with a summary of the project's goals and objectives, and a 'Current status' section with a list of tasks and their progress.

Phase five completed!
You are a star! 🌟

Phase